

Revolutionary Mahdism and Resistance to Colonial Rule in the Sokoto Caliphate, 1905-1906

Secondary source

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Entry tags: Religious Group, African Religions, Arabic, Language, African Religion, Afro-Asiatic, Islam

The Mahdist rebellion of 1905–1906, which targeted the nobility of the Sokoto Caliphate, the 'zarmakoy' (Zarma kings) of Dosso, and British and French colonial rule, was a revolutionary movement. Beginning late in 1905 in French Niger at Kobkitanda, the uprising quickly expanded to Satiru in British northern Nigeria at the beginning of 1906. Disgruntled peasants, runaway slaves, and radical clerics who opposed both the colonial administrations and indigenous authorities made up the Mahdist supporters of the uprising. The 'ulama, affluent businessmen, and nobility were not known to be in favor. Strong class and, consequently, racial divisions were thus mirrored in the uprising. Another significant aspect of the movement that is highlighted by its class tensions and pan-colonial appeal is how revolutionary Mahdism was different.

Date Range: 1905 CE - 1906 CE

Region: Gwandu

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

One of the two capitals of the Fulani Empire

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: <https://wiredspace.wits.ac.za/bitstream/handle/10539/8776/ISS-187.pdf?sequence=1>

– Source 2: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sokoto_Caliphate

– Source 3: <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/4d104b7c2.pdf>

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.africabib.org/http.php?RID=066932386>

Specific to this answer:

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Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: https://www.google.com.ng/books/edition/Sects_Social_Disorder/IIKfBwAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=Revolutionary+Mahdism+and+Resistance+to+Colonial+Rule+in+the+Sokoto+Caliphate&pg=PA52&printsec

Specific to this answer:

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– Source 2 URL: <https://www.africabib.org/rec.php?RID=066932386>

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General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Yes ,because not everyone mean to be at the same religious group ,but can be at the same culture and cultural environment

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↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

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↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Yes ,A member will be assigned through the mean of participation which others may have their interest in the religious groups,so the door is always open to others

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

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Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Yes , because Islam trust in politics and also Islam ruling politics

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↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Apart from this, the polity can contribute but mostly in some cases the religious infrastructure paid for by the religious group

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: No, because the head of the polity can only rule his concerned council, But the head of the religious group in some cases can lead all the society even the head of the polity. Still, in other cases, he can only lead his Ampere. so they can not be The same in other way.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: Because those religious officials are leading the whole society or an ampere and they are leading of almighty Allah, but those political officials are ruling their constitutions, even though others are with also almighty Allah, but few of them.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

Notes: I can say in some other cases , but in other ways are not the same

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 80000000

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Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 50

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Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

- ↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:
 - No
 - ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Powers are inherited:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
 - No
 - ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:
 - No
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - No
 - ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
 - No
 - ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - No

- ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - No
- ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - Yes
- ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - No
- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - Yes

Notes: Yes, but if it is not against God's rules and regulations

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

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- ↳ Are they written:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they oral:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Revealed by a high god:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:
 - No
 - ↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

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Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

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Is iconography present:

– No

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Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: It's obligatory for any Muslim (if he has the money or opportunity to attend the pilgrimage), but if you have less, it is not obligated ,Muslim is simple as it is, but pilgrimage its totally not obligated

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

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Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

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Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: In the world

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

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Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

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Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

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Are grave goods present:

– No

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Are formal burials present:

– No

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Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

– Yes

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- ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: he is alone ,he has no opponent in the world
 - ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: knows what tomorrow is
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:
– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:
– No

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:
– Yes [specify]: speaking, signs and other natural means

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: everything
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– Yes [specify]: make impossible possible
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
 - ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - No
 - ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - No
 - ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Yes [specify]: Its organized only by Almighty god will.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

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Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

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Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

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↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– I don't know

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– I don't know

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: To call believers who have been led astray back into the right path.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: At the day of judgement

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– No

↳ Restoration of the world:

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
– Yes

↳ Other survival condition:
– Yes [specify]: God will judge everyone and have him a survival position

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:
– No

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Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:
– Yes

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
– Strongly present and highlighted
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↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Yes
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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
 - No
 - Yes

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - All individuals within society
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 - Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes

- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes

- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: Fear of God, Humbleness, Patience, Respecting all etc.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

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Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

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Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

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Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

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Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

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Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

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Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: The sacrifices made in these religion are: Charity giving, Zakka, Slaughtering in the day of Eid el-Kabeer etc.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

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Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

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Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

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Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The Aristocracy of Sokoto Caliphate

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Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

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Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

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Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: A group of Voluntary Jihadist are present

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Ajami Form of writing is used in this religious group

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: West Africa, Nigeria Northern Nigeria

Bibliography

General References

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